

Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos

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The Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos (meaning “orphan” in Greek) is located in the higher part of the city of Thessaloniki (Ano Poli), near the western walls. It is dated to the second decade of the 14th century. The title “Orphanos” or “of the Orphans” attributed to the church appears in sources of the 17th and the 18th centuries. It was associated either with the unknown founder of the church and his family, or, with the status of Saint Nicholas, who is considered the patron of widows and orphans. The construction of the monument is probably dated by its wall paintings, dated between 1310-1320. It was initially the *katholikon* (main church) of a monastery, which it is believed to have been founded by the Serbian ruler Milutin. During the Ottoman period, the church was a *metochion* of the Vlatadon Monastery, also located in the upper part of the city of Thessaloniki. Apart from the *katholikon*, what remains from the monastery are fragments from its entrance. The church was originally a three-aisled basilica. It is currently composed of a long, timber-roofed central area, which is surrounded by an ambulatory, covered by lean-to roofs, lower than the one over the central nave. It has in the east two chapels. The nave communicates with the north and south arms of the ambulatory through double-arched openings, while there is a small entrance for passing from the narthex to the main church. Apart from the reused Early Christian capitals, which have two rows of sawn acanthus leaves, as well as the marble iconostasis contemporary with the church, there is no other sculpted decorative elements in the church. Saint Nicholas Orphanos is decorated with wall paintings, revealed in 1957-1960 during the restoration of the monument. They are considered among the finest examples of the mature Palaeologan Renaissance. They date from the decade 1310-1320 and they are associated with the artistic circle of the painters Georgios Kalliergis, Michael and Eutykhios Astrapas, all from Thessaloniki. Their creator is probably the one who also painted the *katholikon* of the Athonite Hilandar Monastery, during the time of the Serbian king Miliutin (1314). In the nave, at the lowest level, are depicted military and healing saints. They are accompanied by representations of the Virgin and Christ, depicted near the sanctuary, and the figures of Saint John the Baptist and Saint John the Theologian, of particular importance for their eschatological meaning. The upper levels of the north, south and west walls narrate the Passion of Christ, while over the west entrance, is depicted the Dormition of the Theotokos. The twelve Great Feasts and scenes narrating the events after the Resurrection of Christ are depicted on the higher parts of the nave and the sanctuary. In the apse is painted the supplicant Virgin between two archangels, and below, the *Melismos* (a symbolic representation of the Holy Eucharist) and Hierarchs. Hierarchs and Church Fathers are also painted on the walls of the sanctuary. Above them, on the east wall, is the scene of the Communion of the Apostles and the Holy Mandylion. On the south wall of the north arm of the ambulatory are depicted Saints, and above, two zones with scenes inspired by the Akathistos Hymn. On the north wall of the south arm of the ambulatory, the lower part is covered with scenes from the Life of Saint Gerasimos and the Burning Bush. In the narthex, apart from the zone of saints, there is an extensive pictorial cycle narrating the Life of Saint Nicholas. There are also scenes from the Lives of other Saints. The monument was inscribed with fourteen more Palaeochristian and Byzantine monuments of the city of Thessaloniki, in the UNESCO List of World Heritage Sites.

Date Range: 1310 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos

Region tags: Thessaloniki, Greece

The Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos is located in the upper part of the old city of Thessaloniki

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kirchhainer, K. . Die Bildausstattung Der Nikolauskirche in Thessaloniki: Untersuchungen Zu Struktur Und Programm Der Malereien. Weimar, 2001.
- Source 2: Tsitouridou, A. Ο Ζωγραφικός Διάκοσμος Του Αγίου Νικολάου Ορφανού Στη Θεσσαλονίκη. Συμβολή Στη Μέλετη Της Παλαιολόγειας Ζωγραφικής Κατά Τον Πρώιμο 14ο Αιώνα. Thessaloniki, 1986.
- Source 3: Mauropoulou-Tsioumi, Chr. Ο Άγιος Νικόλαος ο Ορφανός. Thessaloniki, 1970.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/nicholas-orphanos>
- Source 1 Description: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, detailed description and photos
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh255.jsp?obj_id=473
- Source 2 Description: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, detailed description and photos by the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The church is built in the upper part (Ano Polis) of the city of Thessaloniki

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

One single feature

– Other [specify]: A rectangular building

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The church was originally a three-aisled basilica. It is currently composed of a long, timber-roofed central area, which is surrounded by an ambulatory, covered by lean-to roofs, lower than the one over the central nave. It has in the east two chapels.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: It was initially the *katholikon* (main church) of a monastery

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The church was originally a three-aisled basilica. It is currently composed of a long, timber-roofed central area, which is surrounded by an ambulatory, covered by lean-to roofs, lower than the one over the central nave. It has in the east two chapels.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: It was not reconstructed but modified.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: This is a place of prayer, meditation and worship of God

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: This is a place of prayer, meditation and worship of God

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: This is a place of prayer, meditation and worship of God

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Notes: It is believed that the church was founded by the Serbian ruler Milutin.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the church was founded by the Serbian ruler Milutin.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Earth

– Yes

Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments, binders used for the frescoes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments and binders used for the frescoes

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis and icons (panel paintings). The marble iconostasis is contemporary with the church

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God is depicted

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Virgin Mary, Saints, humans included in the narrative scenes of the pictorial programme

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are included in the narrative scenes of the pictorial programme

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ and Virgin Mary and from the life of Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The pictorial cycle includes scenes inspired by Orthodox hymns, namely Akathistos Hymn

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments are never ornamental. They always describe what or who is depicted

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments are never ornamental. They always describe what or who is depicted

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Simple decorative brickwork on the outside walls

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, seraphim and cherubim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses, Melismos, Mandyllion

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Events from the life of Christ, Saints and Virgin Mary

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Events from the life of Christ, Saints and Virgin Mary

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The pictorial programme of the church includes scenes inspired by hymnography, namely the Akathistos Hymn

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Persons visit the church for praying, meditating and participating to the services

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Persons visit the church for praying, meditating and participating to the services

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Persons visit the church for praying, meditating and participating to the services

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Persons visit the church for praying, meditating and participating to the services

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Divine liturgy and offices

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Impossible to provide an exact number

- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: At least once a week (Sunday service) and on other occasions decided by the priests and/or monks in charge of the monument

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
 - Notes: The Orthodox ritual is followed

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
 - Notes: The Orthodox ritual is followed

- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the building is required for preserving the structure and the wall decoration of the monument.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: Experts from many domains collaborate for the preservation and conservation of the church

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Ephorate of Byzantine monuments of the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports and the Metropolis of Thessaloniki collaborate closely and are in charge of the preservation of this monument and of all the Byzantine monuments of Thessaloniki

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: Festivals are not present. However, the church celebrates on the feast day of Saint Nicholas of Myra, on December 6

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

Notes: The church was previously the katholikon (main church) of a monastery. Thus, religious specialists are not present full time at the monument

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: The church was previously the katholikon (main church) of a monastery. Thus, religious specialists are present part time at the monument

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male priests, monks, bishops etc.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy is the one followed by the Orthodox Church

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The church was previously the katholikon (main church) of a monastery and included back then living spaces for the monks living there

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Xyngoroulos, A.. Οι Τοιχογραφίες Του Αγίου Νικολάου Ορφανού Θεσσαλονίκης. Athens, 1964.

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Mauropoulou-Tsioumi, Chr.. Ο Άγιος Νικόλαος Ο Ορφανός. Thessaloniki, 1970.

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Tsitouridou, A.. Ο Ζωγραφικός Διάκοσμος Του Αγίου Νικολάου Ορφανού Στη Θεσσαλονίκη. Συμβολή Στη Μέλετη Της Παλαιολόγειας Ζωγραφικής Κατά Τον Πρώιμο 14ο Αιώνα. Thessaloniki, 1986.

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Kirchhainer, K. . Die Bildausstattung Der Nikolauskirche in Thessaloniki: Untersuchungen Zu Struktur Und Programm Der Malereien. Weimar, 2001.

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Bakirtzis, Ch., ed.. Άγιος Νικόλαος Ο Ορφανός. Οι Τοιχογραφίες. Edited by Ch. Bakirtzis. Athens, 2003.

Reference: Church of Saint Nicholas Orphanos, Xyngoroulos, A.. “Νεώτεροι Έρευναι Εις Τον Άγιον Νικόλαον Ορφανόν Θεσσαλονίκης”. *Makedonika* 6, no. 1 (1965).